

EXPERIMENTAL MICRO-MECHANICAL CHARACTERIZATION OF INTERLAMINAR SHEAR DEFORMATION IN INTERLAMINAR-TOUGHENED CFRP LAMINATES

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SUMMARY: Tensile tests of CFRP cross-ply laminates with interlaminar resin layers were carried out in a SEM (scanning electron microscope), and microscopic interlaminar deformation and damage near the transverse crack tip was visualized by micro-lines or micro-grids on the specimen edge surface. The local deformation around the transverse crack tip was observed at 20°C, 80°C, 120°C, and 160°C to evaluate the effect of thermal residual stress on the microscopic deformation and damage in the interlaminar region near transverse crack tips. Temperature dependence of interlaminar shear deformation in the resin-rich interlaminar region was clearly demonstrated microscopically. Temperature dependence of the axial COD (crack opening displacement) was also measured. The displacement field of the specimen edge surface obtained from these experimental results were compared with the two dimensional approximate elastic analysis.

KEYWORDS: crack opening displacement, cross-ply laminate, interlaminar shear deformation, micro-line/grid methods, temperature effect, transverse crack, thermal residual stress, Young's modulus reduction

INTRODUCTION

In many applications of fiber-reinforced plastics, they are mainly used in the form of multidirectional laminates. Among these composites, cross-ply laminates have been extensively investigated [1-7] through both theoretical and experimental studies because this is a basic laminate configuration. The failure process of cross-ply laminates is known to involve an accumulation of transverse cracks and delamination.

Most previous studies of the failure process of cross-ply laminates have been focused on the experimental measurement of transverse crack density as a function of applied load or the theoretical prediction of the onset of transverse cracking and its multiplication. In conjunction with the theoretical prediction of mechanical behavior and damage progress of cracked laminates, micromechanical stress analyses of damaged cross-ply laminates have been conducted.

Takeda and Ogihara [2, 3] conducted *in-situ* observation of microscopic failure process in CFRP cross-ply laminates at R.T. and at 80°C. Progressive damage parameters, the

transverse crack density and delamination ratio, were presented. They pointed out that the thermal residual stress had significant effect on the failure process and that quantitative estimation of thermal residual stress was important.

Hashin [4] conducted variational stress analysis for cracked cross-ply laminates under tension and shear, and predicted stiffness reduction. In the analysis, an admissible stress state was assumed and the principle of minimum complementary energy was applied. Nairn [5] extended Hashin's analysis to consider the thermal residual stresses and derived the energy release rate associated with transverse crack formation. The energy release rate was used to predict transverse crack density as a function of laminate stress.

Lee et al. [6] proposed a mathematical model for predicting the stiffness reduction of cracked cross-ply laminates. In their analysis, the principle of minimum potential energy was utilized with assumed displacement fields. McCartney [7] analyzed stress transfer between 0° and 90° plies in cracked cross-ply laminates. The solutions were determined to satisfy the stress-strain-temperature relations either exactly or in an average sense.

In recent years, interleaved laminates have been developed in which resin rich layers are placed in interlaminar regions to enhance the interlaminar fracture toughness of CFRP laminates and to restrict delamination onset. In this paper, micro-lines or micro-grids were printed on edge surface of interleaved CFRP cross-ply laminate specimens to measure the local displacement fields near the transverse crack. Observations are carried out in a scanning electron microscope (SEM) at different temperatures to evaluate the effect of thermal residual stress on the local deformation. Quantitative measurement of microscopic deformation was conducted and the experimental results were compared with the predictions based on two dimensional approximate elastic analysis. Loading-unloading testes were also conducted to obtain the Young's modulus reduction as a function of the transverse crack density. A reasonable agreement between the experimental results and analytical predictions were obtained.

EXPERIMENT

Materials

Two material systems were used. One was interleaved CFRP, T800H/3631-FM300, with epoxy resin (FM300) layers about 100µm thick between 0° and 90° plies. Another was toughness-improved CFRP, T800H/3900-2, with selectively toughened interlaminar layers about 30µm thick at all the ply interfaces. The interlaminar layers have tough and fine thermoplastic resin particles dispersed in the base epoxy resin.

T800H is a high strength carbon fiber. The 3631 is a modified epoxy system with improved toughness compared with a conventional TGDDM/DDS epoxy system. The average thickness of each ply was 0.135mm for T800H/3631-FM300 and 0.190mm for T800H/3900-2. The fiber volume fraction was about 45% for T800H/3631-FM300 and about 55% for T800H/3900-2. The low fiber volume fraction for T800H/3631-FM300 is due to the insert of the FM300 resin film. The laminate configuration was cross-ply (0/90₄/0).

Preparation of Micro-lines and Micro-grids

The micro-lines or micro-grids were made using the photo-lithography technique on specimen edge surfaces. First, the surface of the specimen was polished, then coated by the photo-resist, or photo-chemical reactive resin. The specimen was heated to cure the resist, and the surface was exposed to the light through the photo-mask, or the glass plate with micro-lines or grids. Then the exposed part of the resist was removed in the developer, and vacuum-evaporated metal was deposited on the surface. Finally, the remaining resist was removed in the solvent to prepare the micro-lines or grids on the specimen surface.

Measurement of Microscopic Deformation and Young's Modulus Reduction

Tensile tests of CFRP symmetric cross-ply laminates were carried out in a SEM (scanning electron microscope) with a servo-hydraulic loading machine and a specimen heating unit. The specimen was loaded at 20°C until the transverse crack intervals became uniform, and the images of local area near the crack tip and a whole view of the crack were photographed. Then the temperature was raised to 80°C and the crack was photographed again. This procedure was repeated at 120°C and 160°C. The COD of the transverse cracks and the interlaminar shear strain, γ_{xy} ($=\partial v/\partial x + \partial u/\partial y$) near the transverse crack tip were measured from these photos, where u and v are displacements in x and y directions, respectively (Fig.1). Since the $\partial u/\partial y$ component is considered small, the shear strain was replaced by $\partial v/\partial x$ in the following. Both the average shear strain in interleaf and the shear strain at 90°/interleaf interface were measured.

Loading-unloading tests were also conducted to obtain Young's modulus reduction as a function of the transverse crack density. The loading-unloading procedure cycles were repeated several times with continuous recording of the stress-strain curves. The laminate configurations used in the loading-unloading tests were cross-ply (0/90_m/0) where $m = 4, 8$ and 12 for both material systems.

ANALYSIS

In the present study, stress and displacement fields in an interleaved CFRP cross-ply laminates with transverse cracks are analyzed [8]. The analysis is based on the two dimensional model developed by McCartney [7] which assumes that generalized plane strain conditions prevail. Account is taken of thermal residual stresses arising from a mismatch in thermal expansion coefficients of 0°, 90° plies and the interleaf layer.

Consider a cross-ply laminate subjected to mechanical and thermal loading as shown in Fig.1 in which interleaf layers are of thickness t . In the present study, two cases are considered; (a) the transverse crack tip stops at 90°/interleaf interface, and (b) transverse crack penetrates into the interleaf and stops at 0°/interleaf interface. The displacement in y -direction in interleaf, v_i , and that in 90° ply, v_m , are expressed as

$$v_i = \left(\frac{1}{\mu^i} - \frac{\nu_T^m}{E_T^m} \right) b(x-a)C''(y) - C''''(y) \left[\frac{b}{E^i} \left\{ -\frac{1}{6}(x^3 - a^3) + \frac{1}{2}a^2(x-a) \right. \right. \\ \left. \left. + \left(a+t + \frac{b}{2} \right) \left\{ \frac{1}{2}(x^2 - a^2) - a(x-a) \right\} \right\} - \frac{ab}{6E_T^m} \{a - 3(h+t)\}(x-a) \right] + A_2(y) \quad (1)$$

$$v_m = \frac{b}{2a} \left(\frac{1}{\mu_T^m} - \frac{\nu_T^m}{E_T^m} \right) (x^2 - a^2)C''(y) \\ + \frac{b}{6aE_T^m} C''''(y) \left\{ \frac{1}{4}(x^4 - a^4) - \frac{3}{2}a(h+t)(x^2 - a^2) \right\} + A_2(y) \quad (2)$$

where a and b are thicknesses of 90° and 0° plies, respectively, $C(y)$ is a function found for each case, and $A_2(y)$ is an arbitrary function arising from integration. E , μ , and ν are constants determined from the mechanical properties of the plies and the interleaf material. The shear strain and crack opening displacement are compared with experimental results.

By using the displacement fields obtained above, Young's modulus reduction as a function of the transverse crack density can be derived for each case [8]. The experimental results were compared with the analytical predictions.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Figure 2 shows a transverse crack in a T800H/3631-FM300 cross-ply laminate ($\sigma=216\text{MPa}$, 20°C , where σ is laminate stress). By printing micro-lines, we can clearly observe shear deformation in FM300 layer and damage (fiber/matrix interfacial debonding) near transverse crack tip. By inserting the FM300 layer, delamination from the tips of the transverse cracks were not observed which is due to the enhancement of interlaminar fracture toughness. The transverse crack tip propagates into the FM300 layer at some depth and crack tip blunting can be observed.

Figure 3 shows the temperature dependence of the shear strain for T800H/3631-FM300 as a function of distance from the crack tip. The shear strain at 160°C is much larger than that at other temperatures, which is considered due to the drastic reduction in the shear modulus of FM300 at 160°C . The average shear strain in the interleaf layer is larger than that at $90^\circ/\text{interleaf}$ interface. In Fig.3, the analytical predictions are also shown for Case (b), because it seems more realistic than Case (a). The thermo-mechanical properties used in the analysis are shown in Table 1. The most values in Table 1 are taken from Ref.(9).

Figure 4 shows the temperature dependence of COD as a function of the position in the thickness direction. The experimental results shows that temperature dependence of COD is small. This is due to the combined effect of the decrease in the thermal residual stress and the decrease in shear modulus of the interleaf and 90° ply at higher temperature. In Fig.4, the analytical predictions are also shown for both Cases (a) and (b). Cases (a) and (b) are considered lower and upper bounds for COD. For more quantitative estimation of COD, a model in which a transverse crack penetrates into the interleaf at arbitrary depth is necessary.

Figure 5 shows a transverse crack in a T800H/3900-2 cross-ply laminate ($\sigma = 160\text{MPa}$, (a) 20°C , (b) 160°C). As the temperature rises, the COD in the interlaminar layer increases, while that at the center of the 90° layer changes little.

Figure 6 shows the local highly-deformed area near a transverse crack tip in a T800H/3900-2 cross-ply laminate. It is observed that at 160°C the shear strain in the interlaminar layer becomes rather large. The shear strain in 90° ply, on the contrary, slightly decreases.

Figure 7 shows the temperature dependence of the shear strain for T800H/3900-2 as a function of distance from the crack tip. Larger shear strain is observed in the interlaminar layer at higher temperature, which is considered due to the softening of the interlaminar layer. This corresponds well with the experimental results where the COD in the interlaminar layer magnifies at higher temperature. In Fig.7, the analytical predictions are also shown for Case (b). A reasonable agreement is obtained between the experimental and analytical results except for 160°C . With more proper selection of mechanical properties of interleaf material as a function of temperature, the deformation will be predicted more precisely.

Figure 8 shows the temperature dependence of COD as a function of the position in the thickness direction for T800H/3900-2. Similar to T800H/3631-FM300, temperature dependence of COD is small. This is considered to be due to the reduction in the thermal residual stress and the decrease in the load transmission capability of the softened interlaminar layer. In Fig.8, the analytical predictions are also shown for both Cases (a) and (b). The difference in lower and upper bounds for COD is smaller than for T800H/3631-FM300, because the interleaf thickness is small. Case (b) seems to be a good approximation to this material system.

Figures 9 and 10 show the comparison of experimental results and analytical predictions for the Young's modulus reduction at room temperature in T800H/3631-FM300 and T800H/3900-2 cross-ply laminates, respectively. The analytical results are shown only for Case (a) because the difference between the cases are very small. A reasonable agreement is obtained between the experimental and analytical results. Similar results were obtained at higher temperatures.

CONCLUSIONS

Tensile tests of interleaved CFRP cross-ply laminates were carried out in a SEM, and microscopic interlaminar deformation and damage around the transverse crack was observed at different temperatures by means of micro-lines or grids printed on the specimen edge surface. Temperature dependence of the experimentally-obtained interlaminar shear strain and crack opening displacement were compared with the two-dimensional approximate elastic analysis.

Loading-unloading testes were also conducted to obtain the Young's modulus reduction as a function of the transverse crack density. A reasonable agreement between the experimental and analytical results were obtained.

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Table 1. Material Properties Used in the Analysis.

T800H/3631-FM300			
T800H/3631		FM300	
E_A (GPa)	$169-0.111xT$	E^i (GPa)	$2.65-0.010xT$
E_T (GPa)	$9.62-0.010xT$	ν^i	0.38
G_A (GPa)	4.50	α^i ($^{\circ}C$)	60.6×10^{-6}
ν_A	0.349		
ν_T	0.490		
α_A ($^{\circ}C$)	0.10×10^{-6}		
α_T ($^{\circ}C$)	35.5×10^{-6}		

T800H/3900-2

Base Composite		Polyamide Particle-Dispersed Layer	
E_A (GPa)	$132-0.090xT$	E^i (GPa)	$2.71-0.0105xT$
E_T (GPa)	$8.17-0.007xT$	ν^i	0.38
G_A (GPa)	4.50	α^i ($^{\circ}\text{C}$)	$60.6x 10^{-6}$
ν_A	0.349		
ν_T	0.490		
α_A ($^{\circ}\text{C}$)	$-1.73x10^{-6}$		
α_T ($^{\circ}\text{C}$)	$34.7x10^{-6}$		

T : degrees centigrade ($^{\circ}\text{C}$)

Figure 1. A model of interleaved cross-ply laminate containing transverse cracks in 90° ply. Case (a); Transverse crack tips stop at 90° /interleaf interface. Case (b); Transverse cracks penetrate into interleaf and stop at interleaf/ 0° interface.

Results Prediction
 ○ 20°C △ 80°C — 20°C - - - 80°C
 □ 120°C + 160°C - - - 120°C - - - 160°C

Fig.3 Shear Strain as a Function of Distance from the Transverse Crack Tip in T800H/3631-FM300.

Results Prediction
 ○ 20°C △ 80°C — 20°C - - - 80°C
 □ 120°C + 160°C - - - 120°C - - - 160°C

Fig.4 COD as a Function of Distance from the Central Plane in T800H/3631-FM300.

Fig.2 Transverse Crack Tip in T800H/3631-FM300 (Laminate Stress=216MPa, 20°C).

Fig. 5 Transverse Crack Tip in T800H/3900-2 (Laminate Stress=160MPa, (a) 20°C, (b) 160°C).

Fig.6 Interlaminar Shear Deformation near Transverse Crack Tip in T800H/3900-2 (Laminate Stress=160MPa, (a) 20°C, (b) 160°C).

Results
 ○ 20°C △ 80°C □ 120°C + 160°C + 160°C
 Prediction
 — 20°C - - - 80°C - · - 120°C · - - 160°C

Fig.7 Shear Strain as a Function of Distance from the Transverse Crack Tip in T800H/3900-2.

Results
 ○ 20°C △ 80°C □ 120°C + 160°C + 160°C
 Prediction
 — 20°C - - - 80°C - · - 120°C · - - 160°C

Fig.8 COD as a Function of Distance from the Central Plane in T800H/3900-2.

Fig.9 Normalized Young's modulus as a function of transverse crack density in T800H/3631-FM300 cross-ply laminates (0/90_m/0) at room temperature.

Fig.10 Normalized Young's modulus as a function of transverse crack density in T800H/3900-2 cross-ply laminates (0/90_m/0) at room temperature.